

Gene	localized expression at 24hpf
<i>fosB-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>hes-like2</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>musk-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>six4/5</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>eHand-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>pdgfr-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>mae-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>tbx20-like2</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>fz1-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>gata</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>kielin-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>meis</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>pou-like1</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>pou-like2</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>runt</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>bmp1-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>fgfr-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>fox1</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>hd058</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>k50-5</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>perlecan-like</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>tbx1</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>ret-like2</i>	animal hemisphere
<i>ephrinB-like</i>	animal hemisphere

Gene	localized expression at 24hpf
<i>lhx6</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>sp8/9-like</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>fgfA1</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>fgfrA</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>ax1</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>foxq2a</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>hmx3-like</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>fgfA2</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>rx3-like</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>sfrp1/5</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>dkk124</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>hd146</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>six3/6</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>c-myc-like</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>tolloid-like</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>foxD1</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>wnt7b</i>	vegetal hemisphere
<i>fz5/8</i>	vegetal hemisphere